

IMPROVEMENT OF FOOD SAFETY MANAGEMENT MECHANISM IN OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract: This article contains information about the level of food safety in our country and what is being done in this direction, enriched with personal suggestions and opinions.

Key words: Food products, primary product, rational consumption norm, consumption basket, management, food safety rating, dried fruit, national program.

Introduction

Ensuring food safety in our country is becoming one of the main directions of stable development of the socio-economic situation of the society, improvement of health and life of citizens, national security and stable maintenance of the country's independence. To have a physical and economic opportunity for a sufficient amount of safe food products necessary for an active and healthy life of the population, to improve the quality of products, to ensure price stability, to promote proper and healthy nutrition In order to ensure the health of the population, even at the state level, in the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, in the Action Strategy: **Ensuring** food safety in the country in **2019-2024 directions for approving the program** have been defined ¹.

The objectives of the "**Uzbekistan-2030**" strategy to provide our people with high-quality and nutritious food and to take measures to provide the population with agricultural products . In particular,

- in order to ensure the safe preservation of biological diversity, to establish cultural plantations on an area of 25 thousand hectares every year for the cultivation and reproduction of medicinal and food plants;
- In order to sharply increase the level of productivity and profitability in agriculture, to increase the supply of local vegetable, potato, and potato seeds to 50%, as well as to increase the rate of processing of agricultural products above 25% ; such priority tasks have been set ².

Literature review

¹ Action strategy for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

² "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy.

Nowadays, technology is very advanced and you can find any information online, but still books have shown us the best way in any field. Professor Suzanne Neilson from Australia analyzed harmful substances in food in her book "**Food Analysis**". As our technology continues to evolve at a rapid pace, tried and true methods are still widely used. Part of a food science text series, Neilson, along with other authors, introduces the reader to the basics of analytical processes such as spectroscopy and chromatography. One Amazon.com reviewer says it's "A must for food chemists and food analysts." The book covers many techniques and principles of proximate and specific food analysis. Short and to the point, the writing packs a lot of information into 550 invaluable pages. Another scientist, **Frank Yiannas**, in his book *Food Safety Culture: Building a Behavior-Based Food Safety Management System (Food Microbiology and Food Safety)* writes that he is the food safety director for global brands such as Disney and Walmart. is a proven manager. In addition, he has highlighted in his works that he is the former president of the International Food Protection Association, author, adjunct professor, food system futurist and consumer advocate.

M.M. Azlarova classified the food market in her research as follows:

Figure 1. Classification of food markets according to the main characteristics . [3]

From the data in Figure 1, we can see that there are world food markets, interstate, national, regional and local markets in terms of territorial coverage. According to the level of food supply, the market is divided into exporters and importers. According to the forms and stages of the movement of goods in the field, wholesale and retail markets are divided into long-term storage markets and fast-moving goods markets according to their storage periods. Depending on the signs of the products circulating in the market, food markets, grains, meat, vegetables, fruits, etc.

Methodology

Today, it is important to improve the food security index on a global scale, to deliver food to economically and resource-poor countries. leads to an increase in negative effects.

144 countries are considered as lenders to the World Bank, and this organization has forecasted the number of food insecure people in the countries in 2022 in the World Economic Outlook database. According to the analysis, if large-scale interventions are not implemented, the number of global food-stressed population could exceed **1 billion by 2027** . The Food and

Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) today faces the ambitious task of transforming global agri-food systems to feed a growing population while protecting against adverse environmental impacts. called for more public and private investment.

Food security is a priority for Uzbekistan , and agriculture also plays a crucial role in the country's economic development. The government urged the villagers to actively plant and grow agricultural products on their farms. A sustainable water supply is essential to ensure food security for the population, while ensuring the economic viability of agriculture. If we look at the regions, about **50 %** of the gross domestic product of Khorezm region is supported by agricultural production, 60% of the labor force of the region is **employed** in this field. The availability of irrigation water is important for the agricultural sector and improves the regional economy and population well-being.

" Uzbekistan is a net importer of essential products such as grain, vegetables and sugar, and about **40 percent of** the country's food supply comes from the Black Sea region. Following the global consequences of the war in Ukraine, including the increase in the prices of food and raw materials, food security has become a major concern for Uzbekistan ," said the press release of the OPEC International Development Fund. In June 2022, the OPEC fund announced its \$ **1 billion** Food Security Action Plan for 2022-2025 , which will provide financing for imports of key commodities, thereby helping partner countries to will help ensure sustainable food supply in the medium and long term. The fund provides grants and loans to the public and private sectors of developing countries most affected by the war in Ukraine.

Analysis . Today, the food industry has become a huge industry that is constantly being produced on a global scale. The food industry consists of a global network of manufacturers, wholesalers, distributors and retailers that meet the ever-increasing demand for food products around the world.

Uzbekistan is currently seeking to increase the production and export of food products with high added value. Given the current shortage of capacity in the country's food processing industry, there is considerable scope for growth. Only **15% of the 20 million tons** of fruits and vegetables produced annually are processed for longer storage, while **30% are lost due to** insufficient storage and processing capacity . Only **16 percent of** meat and milk is processed.

In Uzbekistan, by **2026, the goal is to increase the production** of food products to **7.4 million tons**, to increase the processing of milk (32 percent), meat (25 percent), and fruits and vegetables (28 percent). The list of 676 types of technological equipment (including several models of food processing equipment) exempted from customs duty and value added tax upon importation into the republic by the government decision of June 4, 2021 . As of August 2023 , the existing cold storage capacity was 1.5 million tons, which was only 7% of the total volume of cultivated products. The government plans to ³double the capacity of the country's cold storage chain by 2025 . The government's current development plan envisages an increase in processing capacity to 3.4 million tons by 2030, which is 30 percent of Uzbekistan's annual harvest . In 2022, the government allocated \$140 million to banks to provide soft loans for the purchase of trucks, as well as sorting and packaging equipment, and there is an option to allocate another \$330 million. By the decision of the President on September 9, 2020, it was decided to establish the General Directorate for the Development of the Food Processing Industry under the Ministry of Agriculture . The task of this bureau is to create conditions for effective cooperation between agricultural producers and food processing enterprises, to develop a strategy for the development of the food industry of Uzbekistan, to support the establishment of the necessary trade and logistics centers, and to stimulate the export of food products. loaded.

1- **Table.** Food processing market size, in million USD.

	2020 year	2021 year	2022 year	Estimate until the end of 2023.

³ Official site of the International Trade Administration.

Total domestic production	4,215	4,920	5,472	6,000
Total exports	1,336	1,372	1,632	2,000
Total imports	2,197	2,510	3,393	4,000
Import from USA⁴	0.9	1.4	1.2	N/A
Total market size*	5,076	6,058	7,233	8,000
Exchange rates**	10,056	10,610	11,051	12,300

* Total market size = (total domestic production + import) - export.

**Exchange rates = Uzbek soum for 1 dollar .

Conclusions

In conclusion, it is appropriate to use foreign samples to ensure food safety and deliver quality products to the population. As I mentioned above, it is necessary to use the experience of scientists like **Frank Yiannas** . Food products are especially the most important factor of healthy life. Currently, the population of our country is becoming increasingly urban. In this case, the problems of quality delivery of agricultural products to the population are the most urgent. For example, the fact that the governor of Samarkand region, Erkinjon Turdimov , held a meeting regarding the sale of expired products in food stores in the region shows that this topic is very relevant. Also, the head of the region: "Dear shopkeepers , whether you own a shop or sell food, do not be dishonest and do not sell expired products, collect them and take them away." Otherwise , we will have to "collect" you. Especially hand-made baked goods, things that have no source of origin, are not certified, not packaged, and do not have dates written on them, are being sold as buns and cakes. he emphasizes⁵.

Since our country is an agrarian economic country, the food sector and types of food mainly rely on agriculture. Agricultural products are the main part of the food sector and are exported to many countries. Keeping food safe and delivering it safely to the consumer is one of the most urgent tasks. Food waste also affects public health and food safety in our country. The best opportunities for providing processing and packaging equipment are available in the juice, fruit, vegetable, meat and dairy industries. Our government encourages the development of the private sector in these areas . Cardboard, paper, aluminum foil and stretch films are in the greatest demand for packaging materials. Small businesses have a great need for small equipment purchases. For specific opportunities, businesses should contact companies operating in the food processing sector of Uzbekistan . Lactalis, Coca-Cola and PepsiCo are among the major companies currently doing food processing business in Uzbekistan . Local companies prefer to work with a foreign partner and value access to foreign management, technology, technical expertise and export markets.

List of used literature:

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⁴ State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan. Data for 2023 was calculated by the Post using reports on the implementation of company projects. Data on "**imports from the United States**" are from the US Census Bureau.

⁵ <https://www.gazeta.uz/>